

Women in Advocacy- Liberation or Oppression in Contemporary Society

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Abstract

The efforts to change the society must begin from the work sphere, specifically the legal profession. The "legal sphere" is an appropriate starting place for any change to prevail in the society; the basic structure for society emulates from the legal sphere but women are still the primary participants either in the home or 'legal sphere'. Advancement of society begins from the effort to bring effective changes is more likely if that effort begins with the legal sphere. The suppression of gender occurred during the british revolution and after Liberalisation, globalisation and Privatisation resulting in the notion that men should work in the public marketplace while women to be remained in the private realm of the family. Although the status of women has changed, the public-private distinction has not disappeared. Women are expected to perform their traditional domestic roles in addition to their newly acquired professional ones. Consequently, women are hampered by two conflicting perceptions: that women are responsible for private realm of family and public workforce responsibilities. Specific pattern have emerged in the legal profession on the basis of sex discriminating among advocates which failed to recognize the role they have played in perpetuating gender discrimination. Recognizing the commitments beyond the office, adopt positive provisions allowing for such obligations which facilitate the equal participation of men and women both in and out of the workplace. This paper is an attempt to explore the oppression involved in legal sphere and liberal opportunities for women.

Keywords: gender disparity, equity, advocacy, profession, workforce, responsibility.

Introduction

The pivotal role of the legal profession is creating the necessary change within itself so that it may foster change in the rest of society. Advocacy is an organised sector designated in order to influence the positive changes to be achieved in the society. In most cases advocacy set an example directing government or other public bodies.³ Despite changing levels of representation in the judiciary, there had to be greater emphasis on stereotypical attitude towards women. Advocacy may also empower people⁴ by providing the skill to decide and sue for one's right. In spite of this right, the Legal profession did not become a popular choice for women, simply because they were restricted to choose legal profession. Attempts

to raise awareness or educate are possible methods to achieve an advocacy goal, but these will need a change in behaviour to be effective. The number of female legal practitioners is less. Since independence, only 6 women judges have been elevated to Supreme Court out of total 229 judges. Out of 29 Supreme Court judges, only one judgment has been given by a female judge – justice R Banumathi. There are only 63 woman judges whereas 611 male judges. When the Supreme Court Women Lawyers Association brought these facts to the attention of the constitution bench it initiated the process of improving the collegiums alleging a gender bias and discrimination against women in appointment. Further, women faced a lot of problems in practicing in court and thus, the profession itself drives less number of women. As this momentum grows, women's voices get heard more widely and bigger changes can result within communities and throughout society. Despite the injustices they face, women around the world are standing up to claim their rights and to fight inequality.

The pace of modern economic growth today provides ample scope for expansion of employment opportunities for women and vitally induces them for expansion to a great extent to drift their occupational mobility to work as equal partners in the common enterprise the world over. Women today stand for all round competition in almost all the spheres and are found to be in abundant quest for their suitable position in the society. A third systemic entry barrier in the profession concerns women and gender discrimination. It is true that the scales of justice are tilted heavily against women in the profession. For the longest time, it was not considered suitable for women to practice in courts. This explains why we have so few women senior advocates and judges in the profession. Even today, the notion that women are soft, and wouldn't be upto the trials and tribulations of a demanding profession like law, continues to hold sway across towns and cities in India⁵. So clients don't want to engage a female lawyer, unless it's a family law matter. Senior advocates don't give enough opportunities to female lawyers to argue. Finally, the lack of a work-life balance in the legal profession means that even though a lot of women join the profession, very few stick it out. Those who do, admit of doing so at the cost of their personal lives. While there is nothing wrong with some added advantages coming the way of those who hail from a legal background⁶, it is pertinent for legal professionals to enquire into and address the systemic causes that prevent smart, talented people from joining the profession. As lawyers, if we can't make the legal profession equal for all, we should not be so confident about championing constitutional values for others. The aim of the paper is to analyse the perception over women advocates and to know the problems faced by women advocates.

Objectives

The objectives of the present study are to analyse the perceptions of the women advocates about legal profession, Further to know the problems faced by the women advocates on the domestic and professional fronts after joining the profession and to suggest various reformation to exclude gender disparities.

Review of Literature

Women earn about twice as less as men and the gap is getting enlarged day by day. The two main reasons for this wage gap are intermittent in the career of women due to maternity and women are focused only in so called female areas of law⁷. Opportunities of women are restricted due to glass ceilings. The research has found that many women lawyers leave the profession on account of incongruity between parenthood and law. (FACTORS INFLUENCING GLASS CEILING OF WOMEN LAWYERS by Dr. Pavithra S, Dr.G.Barani, Dr. A.D.Shalini Preiya) Women are underrepresented in terms of power, status and pay. The research has also identified that gender

plays a main role, even though it makes no difference⁸. Women are deprived of rights based only on their gender and are not given equal opportunities as men. The research has found that men are good at managing their work and life compared to women. Women opt to quit the profession as they could not compete with the demands of work and family. The study concludes with a note that a women lawyer is evaluated above all else as a women⁹. (Women Entering the Legal Profession: Change and Resistance By: Susan Ehrlich Martin & Nancy C. Jurik) Number of women being situated in the least paid jobs and less number of women are found in highly paid jobs (Spurr 1990). The research has identified that there exists gender inequality between men and women in terms of income, upward mobility, power, autonomy, prospects of growth, and levels of job satisfaction. These differences exist irrespective of their experience, where women having similar experience as men are not given equal opportunity as men. The study has identified discrimination in various aspects like upward mobility, exit and re – entry to practice, in terms of income, area and type of practice and job satisfaction, by excluding women in informal meetings and by refusing challenging assignments. (Women in the Legal Profession by Fiona.M Kay and Elizabeth Gorman) (Aspasia Tsaoussis, 2003) has stated that, Lawyering is one of the sturdiest and most competitive professions, which was once male – dominated profession. But now women started excelling in the field of law equally with men¹⁰. Women have made an excellent advancement in attaining gender justice. But still there are various elements that affect gender equivalence, which is highly challengeable to eradicate. The results of the study prove that gender disparity is highly found in income and rank. The main reason for women to be less successful is that women are over – burdened with domestic work and child rearing duties. The research has found that gender doesn't strong impact on negotiating process. (The Greek Divorce Law Reform of 1983 and its Impact on Homemakers: A Social and Economic Analysis by Aspasia Tsaoussis-Hatzis).

Statement of Problem

Gender discrimination is one of the common disparities that strives in the society, it do exist in legal profession also. Women advocates suffer from various gender disparities irrespective of position vested. Advocacy field has a common notion ie. male dominant field where they thrive for rights but failed to recognise their fellow women advocates. This paper aims to know various struggles faced by women advocates in this field and cause do the same.

Methodology

This research is primarily based on public opinion and reports, hence the study includes both qualitative as well as quantitative method. Since analysing the women in advocacy field and discrimination faced by individuals, the study also includes analytic method. The Data collection Present study is based on Primary as well as Secondary sources of data, which are as–Primary data is collected by collecting questionnaire from general public and the Secondary data is collected through literature of N.G.O. reports, Government Reports, Websites, Research Articles, Newspapers. The Variable used are Independent variable as gender and the Dependent variable of the study are Public opinion on gender discrimination and modernisation and to analyse whether advocacy includes gender disparity. The Statistical Tool used are chi square analysis and Symmetric measures. The Sample size were 1617 samples recorded through non-probability convenient sampling method and the respondents were categorized with the independent variable, “gender”.

Sample Size and Frequencies

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	714	44.2	44.2	44.2
	Female	903	55.8	55.8	100.0
	Total	1617	100.0	100.0	

Sample Size Calculation

The survey was conducted in-order to analyse the gender discrimination in the field of advocacy, where the total sample collected where 1617, the total number of male respondents are 714 and the total number of female respondents are 903.

Tables and Calculation

In this study for each issue a survey is done where a sample size mentioned is taken and the percentage is also mentioned, to determine the validity and the determine the study results chi-square analysis and correlation symmetric measures method is used. when the pearson value of 'Asymp. Sig' value is less than 0.05, the alternate hypothesis is considered and when the pearson value 'Asymp. Sig' value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted. For the determining the hypothesis the variables are cross tabulated.

Hypothesis**Null hypothesis**

Bars and judiciary mustn't associate themselves to address the concern regarding gender disparity

Alternative hypothesis

Bars and judiciary must associate themselves to address the concern regarding gender disparity

1. Gender discrimination has increased during the process of modernisation

H0: there is no relationship between gender discrimination and modernisation

Ha: there is relationship between gender discrimination and modernisation

Table 1.1 Gender Discrimination has Increased During the Process of Modernisation

Crosstab				
Count				
		Whether gender discrimination has increased during the process of modernisation ?		
Gender	male	yes	no	Total
	female	550	164	714
Total		558	345	903
		1108	509	1617

Table 1.2

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	42.917a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	42.213	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	43.710	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	42.890	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	1617				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 224.75.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Table 1.3

Symmetric Measures					
		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	.163	.024	6.636	.000c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	.163	.024	6.636	.000c
N of Valid Cases		1617			

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on normal approximation.

The study has focused on this aspect and responses have been obtained from the law students regarding equal justice to women after the period of modernisation. The study has revealed that a large majority of 588 women constituting 55.8% indicated that women are getting equal preference and rights aren't being curtailed. However, a substantial number of 345 respondent women advocates accounting for 55.8% mentioned that women lawyers are not getting equal rights and they are being curtailed. This is really a discouraging trend and indicates the persistence of gender discrimination in our society. From the above table it was found that the Pearson Chi square value is 0.000 which is lower than 0.05 by which indicates that it is lower than the symmetric value which has proved the alternative hypothesis. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 224.75. Thus it proves that there is a significant relationship between the dependent and independent variable.

Gender discrimination has been practiced in Indian social system in various ways viz., family matters, profession, wages, political and legal rights, etc. The post independence period has witnessed a vigorous fight against this social evil at government and non-government level¹¹, and various legal and constitutional steps have been taken to overcome this ethically unjustifiable approach in our society. Despite all the legal provisions against gender discrimination, discriminatory approach towards women is still prevalent in various walks of life. Women lawyers are entitled to all the rights and privileges available in the legal profession along with their male counterparts¹². They may be related to their legal appointments, assignments, promotions, etc. In case of any unjust treatment women lawyers can question such treatment legally. However, discrimination may occur in certain cases as indicated by a few respondent women lawyers.

2. Advocacy field is an exclusion of gender discrimination

H0: there is no relationship between advocacy field and gender discrimination

Ha: there is relationship between advocacy field and gender discrimination

Table 2.1 Advocacy Field is an Exclusion of Gender Discrimination

Crosstab				
Count				
		Advocacy field is an exclusion of gender discrimination		Total
		disagree	agree	Total
Gender	male	341	373	714
	female	378	525	903
Total		719	898	1617

Table 2.2

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.618a	1	.018		
Continuity Correctionb	5.382	1	.020		
Likelihood Ratio	5.616	1	.018		
Fisher's Exact Test				.018	.010
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.615	1	.018		
N of Valid Cases	1617				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 317.48.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Table 2.3

Symmetric Measures					
		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	.059	.025	2.373	.018c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	.059	.025	2.373	.018c
N of Valid Cases		1617			

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on normal approximation.

The study has focused on this aspect and responses have been obtained from the law students regarding gender disparity in advocacy. The study has revealed that a large majority of 525 women constituting 55.8% indicated that women in the legal profession is no exclusion to gender disparity. However, a substantial number of 378 respondents women advocates accounting for 55.8% mentioned that women lawyers are not discriminated ie. legal profession is exclusion to gender disparity. This is really a discouraging trend and indicates the persistence of gender discrimination

in our society. From the above table it was found that the Pearson Chi square value is 0.018 which is lower than 0.05 by which indicates that it is lower than the symmetric value which has proved the alternative hypothesis. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 317.48. Thus it proves that there is a significant relationship between the dependent and independent variable.

Family and social problems and even professional difficulties may compel the legal practitioners to discontinue their professions some times¹³. This has its implications for the advocates in their professional success or failure. The incidence of discontinuing of legal profession is observed among the women advocates. Marriage and other family problems force a good number of women advocates to discontinue their legal profession. Moreover severe competition from male practitioners and the pressure of the legal workforce many young women advocates to discontinue their profession. Disadvantages of legal profession for women advocates are more than for male advocates. Major reasons identified in this context relate to marriage, financial difficulties, health and other family involvements, etc. Women by temperament are unable to face the tensions arising out of these problems.

Discussion

Work satisfaction or satisfaction in pursuing a particular profession has a tremendous influence in making the career a successful one. Legal profession suits persons with special aptitude and inclination. Women have been entering this profession in good number in recent years which was male dominant earlier.¹⁴ Personal interviews with the selected women advocates has revealed that a large majority of the respondents had the feeling that their choice of legal profession has been right. Such positive impact has much to do with the success of the legal practice by women advocates. Economic compulsions lead to the choice of professions in general and legal profession in particular. Social ambitions of enjoying status and fulfilling one's ambition or passion become secondary or incidental¹⁵. Major reason for joining the legal profession by the women advocates has been economic necessity of becoming self employed as mentioned by majority of respondents. Another economic factor compelling a good number of women advocates was to support the family. However, a few of the respondent women advocates have indicated their status consciousness for taking up legal profession. It has been a passion for a few others to become legal practitioners.

Research provides evidence of women being continuously disadvantaged in the legal profession. At present, changes in the policies and advancements are slow and have not yet produced the changes necessary to ensure that women contribute maximally¹⁶ to all facets of the profession. Legal system in India is not proactive at providing a work atmosphere that would facilitate women function efficiently in the fundamental sectors of the system. The implementation of policies that are gender friendly and which make provisions for both parental leave and flexible work schedules for mothers is essential. Departmental policies and procedures regarding issues on recruitment and promotion must be made transparent. Such policies should make provisions for female lawyers progress. Provision should also be made for an increase in the representation of females in the decision making committees. Women, more than men, need to help other women in the profession¹⁷. Therefore, their reasonable distribution in leadership positions is also necessary for the development of women in the legal system. If the legal profession is to be society's instrument for developing a culture of harmony, sustainable human development founded on equity, justice, unity and yet it lacks in treating legal practitioners with equal rights and opportunity.

Findings

The reasons attributable to the gender disparity in legal profession are several and varied they are:

- Religion
- Marital status
- Racial discrimination
- Patriarchal society
- Harassment and exclusion

Conclusion

A primary objective should be to ensure gender equity than gender equality on the basis of performance one should be known for their ability and not on the basis of sex. In order to recognise this, the stereotypical attitude towards gender must be curtailed i.e. employees' ability are mostly judged on the basis of gender which is rampant in the contemporary society which act as a hindrance for many eligible women candidates in spite of their ability to be enshrined. All decision makers and employees must learn to respect the work performed by an individual not with the notion on gender norms. Basically, employers must recognize that any behaviour or comments that bring a worker's gender to the fore are inappropriate and may cause the employee to question her competence. Some law firms have come up with an idea of organising 'diversity training'¹⁸, which are specialised in order to understand individuals' value, non-compliance with gender disparity and to acknowledge one's ability without any stereotypical attitude. Once employers commit themselves to instituting these programs, could definitely bring a small change in the attitude of women in the legal front, this means that a joint workforce is entrusted to eliminate gender disparity in the legal front. This must start from the basic structure i.e. making law students make them to segregate credibility in elimination & consequences of engaging in overt & covert discrimination.

In Indian context at the Bar and the Judiciary, it requires a specific structural change in order to intensify the concerns regarding gender disparity. The women in the legal profession join together in curtailing this gender disparity right from private sphere to public sphere, without letting any women desparate in their fight against a structural and societal evil. The issues regarding gender stereotypes are mostly covered by women fronts this cyclic structure should be curtailed, that the onus for continuing disparity cannot be laid only at the feet of women this propagating structural bias should be curtailed. It is also important that such groups and associations are with the notion against gender disparity and not to stipulate any caste or class discrimination. The justice dispensing mechanisms can set up a standing committee or an able administrative board with adequate staff and resources to address the issue of gender inequality. The judiciary must associate themselves with groups and individuals beyond their domains in strengthening the concerns of the female members of the system and to sensitise the male members of the Judiciary. The solutions and the suggestions seem to be quite simple and straight-forward because the real challenge does not lie in any system or any structure as such. Hence, their needs to be a holistic approach to address this root of the gender disparity.

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Foot Notes

- 3 (Painter-Thorne and Sneddon 2017).
- 4 (Painter-Thorne and Sneddon 2017; Spillane and International Bar Association 2008).
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